

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D2.2 VITAL-5G experimentation platform - Early (testing) drop

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Contributors and Peer Reviewers

Contributors
Juan Brenes (NXW), Elian Kraja (NXW), Giada Landi (NXW), Ilias Kotinas (WINGS), Kostas Trichias (WINGS), Nikos Tzagkarakis (WINGS), Eleni Giannopoulou (WINGS), Alexandru Vulpe (BEIA), Silviu Ciochina (BEIA), Ion Marghescu (BEIA), Lucian Necula (BEIA), George Suciu (BEIA), Gabriel Petrescu (BEIA), George Iordache (BEIA), Dorinel Filip (BEIA), Nina Slamnik-Krijestorac (IMEC), Vincent Charpentier (IMEC), Olivier Vasseur (IMEC), Andreas Kartakoullis (EBOS), Amro Mobayed (EBOS), Andreas Gavrielides (EBOS), Valentin Carlan (DT), Eva Tilborghs (DT), Athina Ropodi (INCE), Aristotelis Margaris (INCE), Kostas Tsagkaris (INCE)
Peer Reviewers
Athina Ropodi (INCE), Marius Iordache (ORO)

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
GUI	Graphical User Interface
CNF	Cloud Network Function
CRUD	Create Remove Update Delete
EMBB	Enhanced mobile broadband
EXPB	Experiment Blueprint
EXPD	Experiment Descriptor
HTTP	Hypertext transfer protocol
IoT	Internet of Things
JPA	Java Persistence API
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCM	LifeCycle Management
ML	Machine Learning
NBI	Northbound interface
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NFVO	NFV Orchestrator
NSD	Network Service Descriptor
NSO	Navigation Speed Optimizer
OAuth	Open Authorization
REST	Representational State Transfer
SQL	Structured Query Language
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
T&L	Transport and Logistics
UC	Use Case
URLLC	Ultra-reliable low latency communications
UX	User eXperience

VA	Vertical Agnostic
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VS	Vertical Specific
VSF	Vertical Service Blueprint
VSD	Vertical Service Descriptor
VSI	Vertical Service Instance

Executive Summary

Deliverable 2.2 “VITAL-5G experimentation platform - Early (testing) drop”, is the second deliverable of WP2 “VITAL-5G Platform Implementation”, and includes the initial outcomes of T2.1, T2.2, T2.3 and T2.4 in terms of software assets produced for the VITAL-5G platform and the VITAL-5G Network Applications supporting the use cases of the project.

The objective of this deliverable is to document and provide proof of the functionalities delivered as part of the early drop release of the VITAL-5G platform and the VITAL-5G Network Applications. In this sense, this document provides:

- Documentation of the functionalities supported by VITAL-5G platform modules and Network Applications;
- Link to the software artifacts delivered for the early drop of the VITAL-5G platform and a subset of early Network Applications. In particular, links to Gitlab repositories are provided for open-source software, while links to software packages are provided for proprietary software;
- Documentation of the software produced for the early drop of VITAL-5G platform and Network Applications.

The document is structured in two main sections: (i) Covering the VITAL-5G platform modules and functionalities part of the early drop; and (ii) Describing the VITAL-5G Network Applications released with the early drop, with the related service scenarios.

The content of this document builds upon the VITAL-5G platform module software architectures, interfaces and internal mechanisms documented in D2.1 [1] establishing the subset of modules released, the specification of the interfaces supported, and the internal software architecture of the modules. The produced software will feed the integration and testing activities in WP3. Moreover, this deliverable will be used as the basis for the upcoming deliverables associated with VITAL-5G Platform releases.

The software modules of the VITAL-5G Platform described in this document, have been deployed and tested in the development environment of VITAL-5G, while the Network Applications components have been deployed in the testbed environments. This effectively confirms the timely and successful delivery of the software assets produced.

In practical terms this deliverable details the first release of the software blocks and interfaces of five of the core components of the VITAL-5G Platform: Portal Web GUI, Network Applications, Services & Experiment Catalogue, Service Lifecycle Manager (LCM), Experiment LCM and the Blueprint Validation Tool. This release demonstrates the initial catalogue management capabilities, with initial features for validation of the Network Applications syntax and the support for the automated testbed NFV Orchestrator (NFVO) catalogue management. Furthermore, this release covers the service lifecycle management capabilities with the integrated NFVO Network Service lifecycle management. Initial definition of the VITAL-5G Platform experiment catalogue and lifecycle management capabilities is also demonstrated in this release.

From the Network Applications perspective, this release demonstrates four different Network Applications: VA1, VA2, VS7 and VS8, two of which are vertical agnostic and two vertical-specific. The target was set on the demonstration of the Network Applications providing the field sensor data acquisition functionality, which are therefore the base for the elaboration of more complex services. Furthermore, we also demonstrate VS7 which demonstrates the concept of Network Application composition and interfacing to produce complex chains.

Table 1 summarizes the VITAL-5G software assets released in the early drop with the link to the tagged source code for the open-source components, or the link to the software image for the Network Application or components associated with proprietary licenses.

Table 1: VITAL-5G early drop software asset summary

Software component	VITAL-5G responsible partner	Early-drop release link	License
Portal Web GUI	eBOS	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/portal-web-gui/-/tags/early-drop	Apache License 2.0
Network Applications, Services & Experiments Catalogue	NXW	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/OpenOnlineRepository/-/tags/early-drop	Apache License 2.0
Service LCM	NXW	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/service-lcm/-/tags/early-drop	Apache License 2.0
Blueprint Validation Tool	BEIA	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/blueprint-validator/-/tags/early-drop	Apache License 2.0
Experiment LCM	NXW	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/experiment-lcm/-/tags/early-drop	Apache License 2.0
VA1 Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation	WINGS	https://share.wings-ict-solutions.dev/vital5g/	Proprietary license
VA2 Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post processing	BEIA+INCE	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/va2	AGPLv3
VS7 Navigation speed optimizer	DT	https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/vs7/-/tags/early-drop	GPLv3
VS8 Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II	IMEC+SF	https://hub.docker.com/layers/195383878/ninask92/vital-5g/vs8/images/sha256-6dd9756c9ef37a2582cde2de787babe41629394f5eaf63beddedbb984326a743?context=repo	Proprietary license

Most notably, the software produced on this release resulted in the delivery of seven open-source software assets: the five VITAL-5G Platform components, VA2 and VS7.

1 Introduction

One of the key objectives of VITAL-5G is the delivery of a platform to facilitate the T&L service design, lifecycle management, automated optimization and validation on top of 5G-enabled infrastructures, exploiting the novel concept of Network Applications to build and compose new services. Moreover, in order to concretely demonstrate how such Network Applications can be benefited from the features offered by the VITAL-5G experimentation platform, the project will also deliver a set of vertical specific and vertical agnostic Network Applications targeting different T&L vertical sectors. These Network Applications will be available on the VITAL-5G repository in order to enable the design of new services and support the three different Use Cases of the project (see D1.1 [3] and D2.1 [1]). Some of these Network Applications will also be available for 3rd party experimenters, as examples to design and test their own Network Applications or as building blocks to build new vertical services.

The goal of this document is two-folded:

- Document the key services and functionalities of the early drop of the VITAL-5G platform by describing the set of modules, their features, application programming interfaces (APIs) and software license. The focus of this early release is set on demonstrating the service design capabilities (including Network Applications, Vertical Service Blueprint and Experiment Blueprint onboarding and management), with basic support for vertical service lifecycle management and experiment execution.
- Provide a detailed description of the VITAL-5G Network Applications released with the early drop and the supported functionalities. In this sense this document describes the functional blocks of the Network Application, the supported features of each block and the link to the software assets supporting the Network Application logic (and the licenses associated with these software assets).

This document builds mainly upon D2.1 [1], which describes the initial software architectures and high-level interfaces of the platform modules and Network Applications. Additionally, deliverable D2.2 details the early drop specific subset of functionalities and modules implemented, relevant interfaces and Network Application targeted deployments.

1.1 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G's Grant Agreement commitments, map the formal Deliverable and Task descriptions with respect to the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 2: Adherence to VITAL-5G's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
T2.1 Network Applications development (Covered by D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D2.4)	The main goal of this task is the development of the vertical specific and agnostic Network Applications, that will be used in the VITAL-5G use cases and the respective relevant features.	Section 3	Section 3 provides the set of vertical specific and vertical agnostic Network Applications that will be released as part of the early drop release of VITAL-5G and therefore will be available on the Open online repository.
	The first phase of this task refers to the design and	Section 3	In Section 3 the early drop Network Applications are described in terms

	<p>implementation of Network Application in terms of number of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) in a service chain, and placement of VNFs on top of the vertical and cross-vertical infrastructure, based on the use case requirements that are recognized and defined in T1.1.</p>		<p>of functional blocks, CNFs and VNFs. Moreover, this section describes the targeted deployment scenarios, including the 5G networking and the T&L Internet of Things (IoT) devices used in this early drop.</p>
	<p>In the second phase of the task, the developed Network Applications will be available at the Open online Network Application repository to be used by 3rd party experimenters, while the necessary functionality and tools will be developed to allow for the creation, onboarding and instantiation of additional Network Application by other experimenters.</p>	<p>Section 2, Section 3</p>	<p>In Section 2 we elaborate on the initial APIs supporting the Network Application onboarding, service design and service lifecycle management, and the use of these APIs through the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI. This will be common for internal and 3rd party experimenters. In Section 3 we enumerate the early drop Network Applications highlighting which could be potentially used by 3rd party experimenters.</p>
<p>T2.2 VITAL-5G platform enhancement & Open repository development (Covered by D2.1, D2.2, D2.3, D2.4)</p>	<p>The goal of this task is to implement the two main blocks of the VITAL-5G's Open platform, i.e., VITAL-5G portal and Open Online repository.</p>	<p>Section 2</p>	<p>Section 2 describes the VITAL-5G platform modules which will be released on the early drop of the platform, providing details regarding the features supported, the APIs, delivery mechanisms and software code structure for the different components. In particular, this early drop includes the catalogue and validation components of the Open Online repository and the Portal modules for lifecycle management of services and experiments.</p>
<p>T2.3 Network Application verification tools (Covered by D2.2, D2.3, D2.4)</p>	<p>This task deals with verification and validation tools, methodologies and benchmarking procedures. The validation tools will be developed and used to pre-validate the Network Applications (in the lab) and</p>	<p>Section 2</p>	<p>Section 2.4 provides an initial specification of the Network Application blueprint validation tool which focuses on the Network Application blueprint syntax and consistency validation, and validation of the Network Application IoT device</p>

	to fully validate Network Applications using the VITAL-5G platform (in the field).		dependencies in the targeted testbed.
T2.4 Application & intelligence development (Covered by D2.2, D2.3, D2.4)	The main activities of this task are: i) definition and implementation of intelligent applications for the project use cases, ii) definition and implementation of distributed data ingestion, fusion and post-processing techniques for the experimentation data, iii) development of the Intent Based and Diagnostics mechanisms, and iv) (self) optimization of use cases based on intelligence inferred from steps ii) and iii).	Section 3	Section 3 elaborates on the early drop of VS8 which collects and stores information from the vessel's Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), and VA1 which supports the ingestion of IoT sensor data from a wide range of IoT devices. These Network Applications support interfaces for consuming the historical data which shall enable the data ingestion for Artificial Intelligence (AI)/ Machine Learning (ML) algorithms.
DELIVERABLE			
D2.2 VITAL-5G experimentation platform - Early (testing) drop			
The first early testing drop of the VITAL-5G experimentation platform including early versions of the Network Applications, verification tools and vertical applications.			

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The rest of this document is structured as follows:

- Section 2: Provides an overview of the VITAL-5G platform components released in the early drop, together with the description of the supported functionalities and the delivery mechanisms for each module;
- Section 3: Details the list of Network Applications available on the early drop, together with the supported functionality and targeted deployment;
- Section 4: Concludes this document outlining the results achieved with this early drop of the VITAL-5G platform and Network Applications and the following steps regarding the platform and Network Application development and delivery.

2 VITAL-5G experimentation platform early drop

As described in D1.2 [2] the VITAL-5G experimentation platform is mainly composed of two blocks: the Open Online Repository and the VITAL-5G Portal backend. In this architecture, the Open Online Repository provides the services to enable the seamless onboarding and validation of Network Applications in the target environments, as well as the design of complex vertical services and experiments based on the composition of Network Application into service chains. The Open Online Repository implements the services by leveraging Network Applications, Services and Experiments catalogues and the Blueprints validation tools. Furthermore, the VITAL-5G Portal backend provides services to accommodate the service lifecycle management, the execution of experiments and assessment of the service and Network Application validation.

The main objective of this early drop of the VITAL-5G Platform is to showcase the services for onboarding and management of Network Application, Vertical and Experiment blueprints and the lifecycle management of services and experiments. This deliverable includes early versions of the Open Online Repository and the Portal backend components. For the Open Online Repository, this will allow to validate in practice the services, workflows and information models designed and developed in order to support Network Application, Vertical Service and Experiment catalogue management and blueprint validation. Moreover, this early drop of the VITAL-5G Portal backend will support service and experiment lifecycle management over an emulated VITAL-5G testbed. In Figure 1, we depict the software modules of the VITAL-5G platform established in D2.1 [1], highlighting the modules included in the early drop of the platform (see D2.1 [1] for the mapping between the functional architecture and the software components). It is important to highlight that since the main objective is the validation of the services exposed by the platform and the internal workflows, the interfaces towards the VITAL-5G testbed facilities will mostly rely on drivers implementing emulated versions of the VITAL-5G testbed interfaces.

Figure 1: Software components of VITAL-5G platform

In Table 3 we detail the features and services supported the early drop of the platform for each one of the software components released.

Table 3: VITAL-5G platform early-drop modules and features

Software component	VITAL-5G responsible partner	Early drop features
Portal Web GUI	eBOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Application Blueprint onboarding • Network Application, Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB) and Vertical Service Descriptor (VSD) management • Create a graphical representation of the onboarded Network Application Blueprints
Network Applications, Services & Experiments Catalogue	NXW	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onboarding, query and removal of Network Application blueprints over emulated VITAL-5G testbed • Onboarding, query and removal of VSB/VSD over emulated VITAL-5G testbed • Onboarding, query and removal of Experiment Blueprint (EXPB)/ Experiment Descriptor (EXPD) • Representational State Transfer (REST) APIs for the aforementioned functionalities
Service LCM	NXW	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Instantiation and termination of vertical services composed of one or more Network Applications, with basic lifecycle management and interaction with the catalogue. • Basic instantiation on emulated VITAL-5G testbed with driver for OSM NFV Orchestrator (NFVO). • REST APIs for the aforementioned functionalities
Blueprint Validation Tool	BEIA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validation of Network Application blueprint JSON syntax • Validation of IoT data used by the Network Application in terms of coherence, and compliance with the data available from the field
Experiment LCM	NXW	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiment lifecycle management functionalities for experiment creation/termination and execution over emulated VITAL-5G testbed • REST API for experiment management • Interaction with Experiment catalogue to get experiment blueprints/descriptors

In order to ease the software code releases, and overall development of the VITAL-5G platform the different components of the platform are associated with one public and one private repository and grouped together using a GitLab group¹. The private repositories shall be used to perform the code developments, while the public

¹ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform

ones will be used for the official platform releases. At the moment of the platform release, the developments performed on the private repositories shall be pushed to the public ones, and tagged in order to identify the release. Each module repository also contains software related documentation (e.g., OpenAPI specifications [15]), example configurations, and installation instructions. In Table 4 we detail the software license of each platform component and the link to the different software artifacts.

Table 4: VITAL-5G Platform component repositories and licenses

Software component	License	Link to software artifacts (code repositories, software packages)
Portal Web GUI	Apache License 2.0	Code repository: https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/portal-web-gui
Network Applications, Services & Experiments Catalogue	Apache License 2.0	Code repository: https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/OpenOnlineRepository OpenAPI specification: https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/OpenOnlineRepository/API
Service LCM	Apache License 2.0	Code repository: https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/service-lcm OpenAPI specification: https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/service-lcm/API
Experiment LCM	Apache License 2.0	Code repository: https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/experiment-lcm
Blueprint validation tool	Apache License 2.0	Code repository: https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/blueprint-validator

2.1 Portal Web GUI

The implementation of the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI leverages on D1.1 [3], which describes the Use Case (UC) functional and non-functional requirements, D1.2 [2] describing the experimentation workflows supported by VITAL-5G Portal, and D2.1 [1] detailing the software modules of the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI. The input is be translated into technical specifications in this deliverable in order to give a low-level representation of the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI during the implementation plan of the portal.

A four-phase implementation process will be employed to utilize this information, as follows:

- **Phase 1: Consideration of Functional and Non-Functional Requirements**
 - Collect the UCs requirements related to the GUI and consider how the end-user would like to visualize them and the overall vision and goals of the project,
 - Acquire a good understanding about the type and the enclosed information of the data that will be communicated from each UC scenario,
 - Understand the profile of the target audience, the background of end-users including 3rd-parties (e.g., academia or industry), and their privileges and needs.
- **Phase 2: Wireframes and Mock-up Designs**
 - Prepare mock-ups and set up the basic interface structure for the different pages we need, and the information that must be displayed within each page,

- For creating a user-friendly dashboard, we must follow a User eXperience (UX) based approach which takes into consideration the thoughts and reactions of the users, for example: optimization of the interface to avoid unnecessary actions from the user, overall GUI design focusing on target displays to avoid screen adjustments from the user, etc.
- For each element added to the interface, the user flow must be taken into consideration,
- Provide these designs to the UCs leaders and get their approval that everything is based on their needs.
- **Phase 3: Prototype Completion**
 - Initiate the development of the experimenters' portal, based on the Phase 2 designs,
 - Complete the first version of the portal including its deployment on the cloud of the project.
- **Phase 4: Final Version Completion**
 - After concluding the prototype phase, the end-users of each UC will test the portal during WP4 trials on matter of usability, user interface, the integration with the UCs and data presented,
 - The UCs feedback will be used to update the portal and it is expected to address feedback from WP4 trials and be ready for the different scenarios from the UCs.

To complete the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI, we will utilize the Web GUI [8] developed as part of 5G-EVE project [9] and it will be extended to cover the upload, visualization and management of Network Application Blueprints. Additionally, the VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI will be responsible for the KPIs visualization of the experiments conducted at each T&L trial site. We will follow agile interaction design to achieve practical and pragmatic design, short development cycles, and dynamic designs that are responsive to changing needs [10].

The following list has the six main design principles that we will apply through agile interaction design:

1. *Elegance and simplicity*: Unity, refinement, and fitness
2. *Scale, contrast, and proportion*: Clarity, harmony, activity, and restraint
3. *Organization and visual structure*: Grouping, hierarchy, relationship, and balance
4. *Module and program*: Focus, flexibility, and consistent application
5. *Image and representation*: Immediacy, generality, cohesiveness, and characterization
6. *Style*: Distinctiveness, integrity, comprehensiveness, and appropriateness

In Figure 2 and Figure 3 we provide screenshots of the 5G EVE Portal GUI used as starting point, while in Figure 4 and Figure 5 we depict the evolution of these two pages in order to adapt to the VITAL-5G platform specifics. In Figure 2 and Figure 4 compare the landing pages of 5G-EVE and VITAL-5G respectively, showing the main functionalities which are available to the logged user. Figure 3 and Figure 5 show the evolution of the experiment design page, with the introduction of the Network Application button to proceed to the Network Application catalogue management page.

Figure 2: 5G EVE Portal Web GUI home page

Figure 3: 5G-EVE Portal Web GUI - Service and Experiment design page

Figure 4: VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI home page

Figure 5: VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI - Service and experiment design page

In Figure 6 and Figure 7 we also illustrate the interface for onboarding new Network Applications and listing the Network Applications already available in the VITAL-5G Open online repository.

Figure 6: VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI - Network Application onboarding

Figure 7: VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI - Network Application catalogue

Figure 8, depicts the Network Application blueprint visualization functionality of the GUI, where different kind of information are displayed about the description of the Network Application, at which testbed is deployed, its various components and how these components are interconnected.

Figure 8: VITAL-5G Portal Web GUI - Network Application Blueprint Visualization

2.1.1 Baseline software updates

The 5G-EVE portal GUI served as the initial inspiration for the VITAL-5G portal web GUI. It was totally redesigned at the time of the first full release to meet the requirements of the VITAL-5G project. The VITAL-5G GUI will give users access to all of the platform’s backend functions and tools, allowing them to construct their experiments through the wise choice of experiments, Network Applications, and services designs, as well as to deliver an intent-based service. In brief the modifications and updates are as follows:

- **[Software update]** Updated GUI colour schemes, logos and overall panel design to match VITAL-5G document templates.

- **[Software update]** The Vertical Service Blueprint catalogue backend client APIs were updated in order to match the northbound interface (NBI) offered the VITAL-5G Vertical Service Blueprint catalogue backend.
- **[New implementation]** Network Application catalogue management wizards, panels and client libraries were developed to enable the catalogue management through the GUI.
- **[Software update]** The site management panels were updated to reflect VITAL-5G management procedures.

2.2 Network Applications, Services & Experiment Catalogue

In Figure 9, we depict the internal software architecture of this module, highlighting the internal modules released in the early drop of the platform in order to support the functionalities described in Table 3:

- **REST Controller:** This module implements a REST server supporting the catalogue management operations, performing an initial format validation before forwarding the request to the catalogue service module. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.catalogue.nbi* package inside the *vital-5g-catalogue* project. Future releases of this module will also implement the authentication and authorization of the incoming request via the access control module.
- **Catalogue Service:** This module performs an in-depth validation of the request, interacting with the NFVO Sync Manager module for the management of the VNF Packages and NSDs associated with the Network Applications and Vertical Service Blueprints. Moreover, this module interacts with the JPA-based repositories for the management of the database associated entries. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.catalogue.services* package inside the *vital-5g-catalogue* project.
- **JPA-Based repositories:** This module mediates between the Catalogue Service and the database providing simplified interfaces for the management of the database records. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.catalogue.repos* package inside the *vital-5g-catalogue* project.
- **NFVO Synch Manager and NFVO Catalogue Service:** These two modules are responsible for providing an unified interface for the management of the NFVO VNF and NSD catalogue management interface of the VITAL-5G testbeds, and automatically syncing the NFVO catalogue based on the Network Application and Vertical Service Blueprint catalogue operations. For this release, this module will emulate the VITAL-5G testbed interface responses. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.catalogue.sbi* package inside the *vital-5g-catalogue* project.
- **SQL database:** The database created to support the registries associated with the different catalogues.

This module is released as open source, using an Apache 2.0 license, and the source code is available in the project GitLab repository ². The code is divided in two maven projects:

- Information models and interfaces (*vital-5g-catalogue-interfaces*): This maven project contains the specification of the information models of the different blueprints and descriptors, and the interfaces describing the catalogue operations. This project is used as a dependency by the *vital-5g-catalogue* project, and is meant to be used also by other internal modules of the platform in order to interact with this module.
- Catalogue application (*vital-5g-catalogue*): This a spring-boot based maven project, implementing the modules depicted in Figure 9, and responsible for providing the Java executable JAR package.

² https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/OpenOnlineRepository

GET	/portal/catalogue/netapppackages	List All Network Application Packages	▼
POST	/portal/catalogue/netapppackages	Onboard a Network Application Package	▼
GET	/portal/catalogue/netapppackages/blueprint	Query Network Application Blueprints	▼
GET	/portal/catalogue/netapppackages/{netapppackageId}	Get a Network Application Package	▼
PUT	/portal/catalogue/netapppackages/{netapppackageId}	Update a Network Application Package	▼
DELETE	/portal/catalogue/netapppackages/{netapppackageId}	Delete a Network Application Package	▼

Figure 10: Early drop Network Application Package Management endpoints

In a similar manner Figure 11 and Figure 12 depict the endpoints enabling the management of the catalogue of VSBs and VSDs.

VSB Catalogue API Vertical service blueprint REST Controller ⏶

GET	/portal/catalogue/vsbs/{vsbid}	Get a VSB	▼
PUT	/portal/catalogue/vsbs/{vsbid}	Update a VSB	▼
DELETE	/portal/catalogue/vsbs/{vsbid}	Delete a VSB	▼
GET	/portal/catalogue/vsbs/{vsbid}/nsd	Get a NSD	▼
PUT	/portal/catalogue/vsbs/{vsbid}/nsd	Update NSD	▼
GET	/portal/catalogue/vsbs	List All VSBS	▼
POST	/portal/catalogue/vsbs	Create a VSB	▼

Figure 11: Early drop Vertical Service Blueprint Management endpoints

VSD Catalogue Vertical Service descriptor management REST API ⏶

GET	/portal/catalogue/vsds	List All VSDS	▼
POST	/portal/catalogue/vsds	Create a VSD	▼ ←
GET	/portal/catalogue/vsds/{vsdescriptorId}	Get a VSD	▼
PUT	/portal/catalogue/vsds/{vsdescriptorId}	Update a VSD	▼
DELETE	/portal/catalogue/vsds/{vsdescriptorId}	Delete a VSD	▼

Figure 12: Early drop Vertical Service Descriptor Management endpoints

Following the CRUD operations of the VITAL-5G Network Application, Services and Experiment catalogues, we use the identifier of the resource optionally combined with an operation specific request and response. In Figure 13 we illustrate the Network Application package onboarding request, which contains the ZIP compressed file of the Network Application package, and in Figure 14 we illustrate the Network Application blueprint retrieval response. We refer to the OpenAPI specification of this module, referenced in Table 4, for further details regarding the operations and their associated requests and responses.

Figure 13: Network Application Package onboarding request

Figure 14: Get Network Application blueprint response

2.2.1 Baseline software updates

The Network Application, Service and Experiment Catalogue module used the 5G-EVE Portal Catalogue module (see 5G-EVE D4.1 [13], for further details) as a software baseline. This section covers the updates and modifications to the software baseline introduced by VITAL-5G, and will be extended in future deliverables with the updates introduced by each release. In this sense, this module has been designed using the 5G-EVE Portal Catalogue software architecture, information models and internal catalogue management workflows as a

starting point. In terms of software code, most of Catalogue Service, REST controller and JPA-repositories of the 5G-EVE Portal Catalogue have been re-used and extended for the implementation of the VITAL-5G catalogue. In parallel, new data models (with the respective JPA-repositories and REST controllers) and new internal modules have been developed from scratch in order to implement the Network Application-specific functionalities and enable the integration with the rest of the VITAL-5G platform. In details, the software updates and the new implementations developed so far are the following (to be extended in future deliverables):

- **[New implementation]** Development of Network Application blueprint data model, REST controllers and catalogue services for onboarding/queries of Network Application packages and blueprints, and JPA repositories related to the Network Application blueprint data model. The concept of Network Application was not present in 5G EVE [9], and therefore all the related functionalities in the Network Application catalogue have been added in VITAL-5G. Where possible, some of the common information elements of the VSB data models were reused and extended.
- **[Software update]** Changes in the information models of VSBs, EXPBs, VSDs and EXPDs. In 5G EVE, the experiments and vertical service instances were tightly coupled, and in practice a service instance was dependent on a specific experiment. In VITAL-5G we removed this dependency, decoupling vertical service and experiment instances, so that the user can directly manage the service lifecycle without any binding to experiment executions. At the catalogue level, this has implications on the VSB, ExpBs and TCBs data models, which have been updated (together with the respective JPA repositories, where needed).
- **[New implementation]** Development and integration of NFVO Synch Manager. In 5G EVE the synchronization between the 5G EVE Portal Catalogue and the testbeds' NFVO catalogues was performed by the 5G EVE InterWorking Layer. In VITAL-5G this functionality has been moved directly in the VITAL-5G Catalogue. This required the development of the internal module logic, the driver to interact with the OSM catalogues deployed in each testbed and the integration in the catalogue management workflows.

2.3 Service LCM

In Figure 15, we depict the internal software architecture of this module, as established in D2.1 [1], highlighting the components which will be part of the early drop of the platform in order to implement the features detailed in Table 3:

- **REST Controller:** Implements a REST server responsible for receiving the service lifecycle management requests, perform an initial validation and forward the request to the Service LCM Engine. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.nbi* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project. Future releases of this module will also include the interaction with the access control module for the authentication and authorization of the requests.
- **Service LCM Engine:** This module processes all the service lifecycle management requests, performing and in-depth validation and is responsible for creating the specific service instance managers, and the forwarding of the requests to the specific manager. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.engine* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.
- **Vertical Service Instance (VSI) Manager:** This module processes the lifecycle management requests for one specific service instance, implementing the finite state machine associated to the instance, and interacting with other modules in order to trigger actions associated with the different lifecycle management events. In this release, this module interacts with the: (i) VSI Record Manager to update the instance status and information; (ii) Open online repository service, to retrieve the Network Application and Vertical Service blueprint and descriptors; (iii) NFVO service, to trigger the network service level lifecycle management events (for this release the interface with the testbeds will be emulated). The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.manager* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.

- **VSI Record Manager:** This module mediates with the Postgres DB [7] to manage the service instance records. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.repo* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.
- **Open online repository Service & Client:** These two modules mediate between the service lifecycle management module and the Network Application and Services Catalogues implementing the logic for the retrieval of the Network Applications and Vertical Service Blueprints and Descriptors via a REST client. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.sbi.catalogue* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.
- **NFVO Service & NFVO client:** These modules mediate between the VSI Manager and the specific testbed NFVO in order offering a unified interface for the network service lifecycle management operations. For this release we target an initial integration enabling the instantiation and termination of the network services associated with the vertical services. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.sbi.nfvo* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.
- **Multi-site inventory service:** This module is used to mediate between the component of the vertical service lifecycle management, and the multi-site inventory catalogue. In this early drop release, this module will emulate the interaction with the multi-site inventory to retrieve the credentials and endpoints required to interact with the testbed NFVO. The source code of this module is located in the *it.nextworks.lcm.vs.sbi.siteinventory* package of the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project.

Figure 15: Service Lifecycle Manager internal software architecture

This module is released under an Apache 2 license, and the source code is available in the project GitLab repository (see Table 4). The code is divided in two maven projects:

- *Vital-5g-service-lcm-interfaces:* This project contains the definition of the messages, the interfaces and the information elements used to interact with this module. It is used as a dependency in the *vital-5g-service-lcm* project and it is meant also to be used by other modules of the platform.
- *Vital-5g-service-lcm:* This contains the implementation of the sub-modules of the service lifecycle manager, as detailed previously.

As detailed in Table 3, this module will support instantiation and termination of vertical services. In Figure 16 we depict the API endpoints which will be supported on the early drop of this component. We refer to the OpenAPI specification of this module, available in Table 4, for the specific request and responses used on each endpoint.

Vertical Service LCM API VS LCM Rest Controller	
GET	/vs/basic/vslcm/vs Get Vertical Service Instances
POST	/vs/basic/vslcm/vs Instantiate Vertical Service
GET	/vs/basic/vslcm/vs/{vsiId} Get Vertical Service Instance
DELETE	/vs/basic/vslcm/vs/{vsiId} Delete a Vertical Service Instance
POST	/vs/basic/vslcm/vs/{vsiId}/terminate Terminate Vertical Service Instance
GET	/vs/basic/vslcm/vsId Get Vertical Service Instance IDs
POST	/vs/basic/vslcm/vs/{vsiId}/use Use Vertical Service Instance
POST	/vs/basic/vslcm/vs/{vsiId}/release Release Vertical Service Instance

Figure 16: Early drop Service Lifecycle Management endpoints

2.3.1 Baseline software updates

As described in D2.1 [1], the Service LCM module used the 5G-EVE Experiment LCM module (see 5G-EVE D4.1 [13], for further details) as software baseline. This section covers the updates and modifications to the software baseline introduced by VITAL-5G, and will be extended in future deliverables with the updates introduced by each release. In this sense, this module has been designed using the 5G-EVE Experiment LCM software architecture, API and internal instance management workflows as starting point. In this manner, most of vertical service lifecycle management engine and managers, REST controller and JPA-repositories software code of the 5G-EVE Portal module has been re-used. In this regard, the main modifications performed was the decoupling of the vertical service and experiment lifecycle management. In particular for this module all the experiment instance related workflows were removed. In parallel, updates and new implementations were performed to interact to VITAL-5G specific modules. In detail:

- **[Software update]** Decoupling of vertical service and experiment instance lifecycle management: The REST API was updated to enable vertical service instance management. The internal module workflows and messages were updated to eliminate the dependency with experiment instance specific information. Experiment instance specific workflows (e.g., execution, termination) were completely removed.
- **[New implementation]** Network Application catalogue client: The Network Application catalogue client to interact with the catalogue module has been developed using the VSB/ExpB clients available from 5G-EVE as reference.
- **[New implementation]** NFVO Lifecycle Management: In 5G-EVE the lifecycle management of the network services was performed through a ETSI SOL based lifecycle management interface implemented by the 5G-EVE InterWorking Layer, which was ultimately responsible of implementing the drivers towards the different sites. In VITAL-5G we use a driver-based approach at the Service LCM level to directly interact with the testbed NFVOs. This required the development of the NFVO Service and specific clients.

2.4 Blueprint Validation Tool

As presented in D2.1 [1], the Network Application validator is based on a static validator prior to Network Application runtime together with a dynamic KPI monitoring and validator tool during onboarding/runtime. During the early drop of the Network Application validator tool, the static validator tool will be introduced. The main functionality is to validate the blueprint of the Network Application. Figure 17 shows the positioning of the component within the overall tool high level architecture. The functionality of each sub-module is as follows:

- Apache Kafka Metric Bus is a streaming platform used to capture real-time data from event sources such as databases, sensors, mobile devices, cloud services, and software applications in the form of streams of events; storing these event streams durably for later retrieval; manipulating, processing, and reacting to the event streams in real-time as well as retrospectively; and routing the event streams to different destination technologies as needed.
- Kafka Exporter is used to improve the monitoring of Apache Kafka brokers and clients by extracting additional valuable data from them related to clearing, consumer groups, delays and consumer topics.
- Static validator tool is further detailed next.

Figure 17: 5G Network Application validator tool high-level architecture.

A detailed view of the two software modules of the static validator tool is illustrated in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Detailed view of the static validator tool

As such the static validator is split into two main modules:

- **JSON syntax validator**

It is a checker of the validity of the Network Application JSON blueprint. It will detect and point out the line number(s) of the code containing errors. Some of the common rules that will be validated are:

- Data is in name-value pairs
 - Data is separated by commas
 - Objects are encapsulated within the opening and closing curly brackets
 - An empty object can be represented by {}
 - Arrays are encapsulated within opening and closing square brackets
 - An empty array can be represented by []
 - A member is represented by a key-value pair, contained in double quotes
 - Each member should have a unique key within an object structure
 - The value of a member must be contained in double quotes, if it is a string
 - Boolean values are represented using the true or false literals in lower case
 - Number values are represented using double-precision floating-point format and should not have leading zeroes
 - “Offensive” characters in a string need to be escaped using the backslash character “\”
 - Null values are represented by the null literal in lower case
 - Dates, and similar object types, are not adequately supported and should be converted to strings
 - Each member of an object or array value must be followed by a comma, except for the last one
 - The standard extension for the JSON file is ‘.json’
 - The mime type for JSON files is ‘application/json’.
- **IoT sensor data validator**

It will validate the sensor data coming from the testbed(s). Some of the rules validated are:

- Data coming from sensor X exists
- Data is valid. Some example validation methods:
 - Zero value detection
 - Flat line detection
 - Minimum and maximum values detection
 - Minimum and maximum thresholds based on last values
 - Statistical tests
- Data is complete

If a Network Application cannot be validated, the Network Application developer will need to modify it in order to be validated and then deployed.

2.4.1 Baseline software updates

The Network Application validator is based on the 5G-EVE blueprint validator, but with several major enhancements. In particular, the module has been revamped so it may work with VITAL-5G models and interact with other VITAL-5G modules:

- **[Software update]** Most of the validation procedure has been reused, but it has been adapted to validating the Network Application against the models (blueprints, descriptors, etc.) developed in VITAL-5G
- **[New implementation]** The Network Application validator has been redesigned to run as a web application, packaged as war file and deployed in an Apache Tomcat³ container.
- **[New implementation]** Simple REST OpenAPI has been developed for using the Network Application validator to validate Network Application blueprint syntax.

³ <https://tomcat.apache.org/>

2.5 Experiment LCM

The internal software architecture of the Experiment LifeCycle Manager module is shown in the following Figure 19. The highlighted internal modules are those released in the early drop of the platform in order to support the functionalities described in Table 3:

- REST Controller:** This module implements a REST server supporting the experiment management, performing the authentication and authorization of the incoming request. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.experiment.nbi* package inside *vital-5g experiment-lcm* project. Each request of experiment creation/execution or termination is forwarded to the Experiment Execution Coordinator.
- Experiment Execution Coordinator:** This module handles the lifecycle management of the experiments. The module is triggered by the REST Controller. It interacts with the Experiment Instance Manager, which is in charge of the lifecycle management of the single experiment execution, and the SQL database used for the persistence of the experiment data. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.experiment.coordinator* package inside the *vital-5g experiment-lcm* project.
- Experiment Instance Manager:** This module is responsible of handling the lifecycle management of an experiment instance. An experiment instance manager is instantiated each time a new experiment execution is requested. It is in charge of the management of the experiment instance, following the finite state, and it interacts with the external components of the VITAL-5G Platform. In this early release it interacts only with the Catalogue Service. The source code of this module can be found inside the *it.nextworks.experiment.manager* package inside the *vital-5g experiment-lcm* project.
- JPA-based repositories, SQL database and Experiment LCM SBI services:** The JPA-based repositories is responsible for the management of the database records that are stored in the SQL database component. The Experiment LCM SBI services implements the interaction with the other VITAL-5G platform components, allowing the Experiment Instance Manager to have the necessary data to run the experiment (i.e.: IP addresses of the different vertical services) or enabling monitoring and result analysis for the running experiment instance.

Figure 19: Experiment LifeCycle Management internal software architecture

The Experiment LCM module is released as open-source, using the Apache 2 license. The source code is available in the GitLab repository ⁴.

- Experiment lifecycle management functionalities for experiment creation/termination and execution over emulated VITAL-5G testbed
- REST API for experiment management
- Interaction with Experiment catalogue to get experiment blueprints/descriptors

This early version of the Experiment LCM supports the creation, termination and execution of an experiment in an emulated VITAL-5G environment. It implements the interaction with the Network Applications, Services & Experiment Catalogue, allowing to retrieve the blueprints and the descriptors of a given Vertical Service, and finally it contains the REST API related to the management of the experiment, as depicted in the following Figure 20.

Experiment LCM Operations		^
GET	/portal/elcm/experiment List all experiments available for execution	∨
POST	/portal/elcm/experiment Create a new Experiment	∨
GET	/portal/elcm/experiment/{id} Get experiment identified by experiment instance identifier	∨
DELETE	/portal/elcm/experiment/{id} Terminate experiment identified by experiment instance identifier	∨
GET	/portal/elcm/experiment/{id}/execution List all experiment execution available related to a single experiment instance	∨
POST	/portal/elcm/experiment/{id}/execution Requests a new experiment execution	∨
GET	/portal/elcm/experiment/{id}/execution/{executionId} elcmExperimentExecutionsIdGet	∨
POST	/portal/elcm/experiment/{id}/execution/{executionId}/stop elmcExperimentExecutionsIdAbortPost	∨

Figure 20: Early drop Experiment LCM Manager endpoints

The creation of a new experiment requires as input a set of data, as depicted in Figure 21, containing the identifiers of the vertical service and the experiment descriptor related to the vertical service to be executed. Optionally, a list of configurations can be sent over this request. Figure 22 depicts the response of the operation, when this is properly executed, returning the identifier of the newly experiment instance created. Further details regarding the set of operations available for the Experiment LCM module are made available over the OpenAPI specification available in the GitLab repository (see Table 4).

⁴ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/experiment-lcm

Figure 21: Experiment creation request

Figure 22: Experiment creation response

2.5.1 Baseline software updates

As initially described in D2.1 [1], the Experiment LCM module of VITAL-5G inherits part of the source code and architecture from the 5G-EVE Service LCM and Experiment Execution Manager. From the code perspective, a part of the REST Controller, Experiment Execution Coordinator, Experiment Instance Manager and JPA-based repositories was re-used from the original modules. The updates and modifications to the software baseline introduced in this release are as follows (an updated list will be provided in future deliverables):

- **[Software Update]** Experiment Lifecycle management and execution decoupling: In 5G EVE the service and experiment instances were coupled together. The platform did not offer the possibility of running a vertical service instance without running an experiment. In VITAL-5G, on the other side, we decoupled the experiment instance management and execution from that of the service, removing all the service instance management dependencies and workflows from the source code.

3 VITAL-5G Network Applications early versions

In this section we present a selection of early versions of the Network Applications. The development of these Network Applications can be started prior to that of other Network Applications, for which the complete list and definition was provided in deliverable D2.1 [1]. For these early versions of the Network Application, a development and delivery requirements have been defined, as well as a set of features to be developed. The features included for each early version are summarized in Table 5. The involved partners, delivery and license information are summarized in Table 6. It is worth to highlight this early drop includes two different Vertical Agnostic (VA), and two Vertical Specific (VS) Network Applications which will be used to implement services across the three use cases of the project.

Table 5: Network Application early drop functionalities

Network Application Code	Network Application Name	List of Features
VA1	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IoT controller for the two-way interaction with IoT devices • MQTT/HTTP Gateway enabling the communication between off-site and on-site infrastructure • Rule engine for decision support • Persistence service providing persistence and caching services to all other Network Application components
VA2	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ingestion of data from various sources - from UC2 Preliminary data analytics • Connectors for acquisition of batch data and ingestion to data persistence module for further pre-processing.
VS7	Navigation speed optimizer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial integration with VS8 to make an initial call and send the geodata • API to retrieve updated speed from other Network Applications.
VS8	On board data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preliminary data collection • Data Proxy Server with Subscriber defined for data collection from vessel • Data manager & Data storage, and Public interface that exposes data either through a REST API, or through a pub/sub mechanism (subscribers running in other Network Applications)

Table 6: Network Application early drop partners involvement, delivery method, and license

Network Application Code	Partners involved	Delivery method (Software image/Package/repository)	License
VA1	WINGS	VM Image: https://share.wings-ict-solutions.dev/vital5g/	Proprietary license
VA2	BEIA+INCE	Source code : https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/va2	AGPLv3
VS7	DT	Source code: https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/vs7	GPLv3
VS8	IMEC+SF	Docker repository: https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/ninask92/vital-5g , Docker image: https://hub.docker.com/layers/195383878/ninask92/vital-5g/vs8/images/sha256-6dd9756c9ef37a2582cde2de787babe41629394f5eaf63beddedbb984326a743?context=repo API specification: https://app.swaggerhub.com/apis/imec-vital-5g/VS8/1.0.0	Proprietary license

3.1 VA1 Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation

3.1.1 Early drop features

The VA1 Network Application with title “Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion and automation” will be responsible for the data ingestion and two-way communication with on-site equipment, decision support using rules and inference, monitoring and field assistance. The components and architecture of the Network Applications have been described in deliverable D2.1 [1]. The first version of VA1 will include a subset of the features of the overall architecture:

- **Core IoT Controller:** the main application logic layer which combines data (events and states), and services to facilitate the two-way interaction with the monitored and controlled IoT devices. It connects together and synchronizes the whole Network Application infrastructure and services by the means of a common event loop and state machine.
- **MQTT/HTTP:** enabling the communication between off-site and on-site infrastructure. Raw data from on-site equipment and environmental sensors are collected in real time through the MQTT and REST API endpoints. Two-way communication is achieved by providing feedback and control commands to the on-site equipment through the same protocols.
- **Reasoning engine:** this early drop will include an automation rules engine and transformation services to provide decision support.
- **Persistence engine:** providing persistence and caching services to all other Network Application components. This early drop will include basic persistence of IoT states.

3.1.2 IoT Devices used

The early drop of VA1 will not include any physical IoT devices. A warehouse environment and AGV simulator will be used for testing the functional operation of this early drop of the Network Application.

3.1.3 5G networking

Since the early drop of VA1 will not include any physical IoT devices, communication over 5G or other network infrastructure will not be required.

3.1.4 Software Licenses and deployment information

The components of Network Applications VA1 will be provided either as a Virtual Machine image (see Table 6).

The VA1 Network Application will include open-source and closed-source components. The closed-source components will be covered by a proprietary license (provided by Wings ICT Solutions) which will allow the usage of the Network Applications within the scope of VITAL-5G, both by the VITAL-5G partners and 3rd-party experimenters.

3.1.5 Baseline software updates

The work for VA1 is not based on any previous EU projects. The integrated functionality has been developed by WINGS in the context of VITAL-5G and is part of the WINGS Chariot proprietary solution.

3.2 VA2 Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post processing

3.2.1 Early drop features

VA2 supports data ingestion, fusion and post-processing functionalities from distributed data sources. The components and architecture of VA2 have been described in Section 3.2.2 in the deliverable D2.1 [1]. The first version of VA2 will include a subset of the features provided in D2.1:

- **Testbed collector – from UC2:** Within VA2 we will perform ingestion of data from various sources, whether one or multiple T&L facilities or external sources. In this early drop we will ingest data from sources (IoT devices) specific to use case 2.
- **Data Collection component:** The data collection component is responsible for the collection of data through the southbound interfacing (via connectors). Its full version will have capabilities for acquisition of both streaming and batch data through HTTP REST APIs querying directly the data source or through message bus services, at various rates. For this early drop, the following features will be available:
 - **External endpoint to data collection:** At this stage, the appropriate connectors have been developed that will ensure the acquisition of batch testbed data through HTTP REST APIs from the data sources available at this stage.
 - **Internal endpoint to Data Persistence module (for raw data ingestion):** The collected data will then be able to be ingested in a distributed filesystem which will allow for storage of structured and unstructured data. More specifically, Apache HDFS [4] storage layer coupled with Apache Hive [5] -an SQL tabular data storage layer- and Trino [6] an open-source distributed query engine are the selected technologies.

3.2.2 Early drop software architecture

Figure 23 illustrates the high-level architecture of VA2 and pinpoints the early drop components that are envisioned for this release, as it was described in Section 3.2.1.

Figure 23: VA2 high-level architecture

3.2.3 IoT devices used

- **AIS transponder (SAAB R4 or Periskal PM-1):** provides data about the type of ship, the position of the ship, the speed of the ship, the angle made relative to the North direction, the type of voyage to be made, the estimated time to the end of that trip.
- **ACTISENSE DST 2 converter:** device to which the depth sensor is connected. It basically transmits pulses with a frequency of 200kHz (in the field of ultrasound) to the depth SENSOR (Airmar SS505). The ultrasonic wave generated by the sensor propagates to the bottom of the water.
- **PLC (Siemens IoT 20xx or Raspberry PI):** a digital or analog signal adder and their transformation into digital signals converted into a protocol recognized by its peripherals (e.g., 5G router).

3.2.4 5G networking

The early drop of VA2 has 5G connectivity in ORO testbed, URLLC and EMBB network slice implementation (we refer to D3.2 [14] for further details regarding the network slices provisioned in the testbed).

3.2.5 Software licenses and link to repositories

The software components of VA2 produced in the project will be released as open source, and code is available in the project GitLab repository (see Table 6).

3.2.6 Baseline software updates

The development of VA2 has been entirely performed within VITAL-5G using software assets developed within the context of VITAL-5G or based on INCE's proprietary solutions.

3.3 VS7 Navigation speed optimizer

The Navigation Speed Optimizer (NSO) uses APIs to retrieve the real-time data needed to calculate the optimal navigation speed for a vessel. Figure 24 below presents the NSO software architecture.

Figure 24: VS7 NSO component early drop architecture

As seen in Figure 24, the data is collected from two sources: (i) client applications (i.e., other Network Applications) and (ii) an inland navigation routing API. The client application, VS8, sends geodata of the vessel's current location and of the destination of the voyage to the NSO API. Based on these data, the inland navigation routing API, in this case the VisuRIS API, can retrieve the inland navigation route. Hence, it can calculate the distance to be sailed.

In addition to the geodata, the client application, VS5, also sends the time by which the vessel should be at its destination. This allows to calculate how much time remains for the vessel to sail to its destination. This data (i.e., the geodata, the navigation route and the time to arrive at the destination) is then used as input to the NSO algorithm. The optimal navigation speed is calculated as the division of the distance to the destination by the time remaining. The calculated optimal speed in kilometres per hour is then being converted to knots.

The optimal navigation speed is then published in a topic on the queue to which the client application can subscribe to retrieve the optimal navigation speed and integrate it into the vessel navigation dashboard.

Since VS5 is not being released in the first drop, the first version of the NSO will only include the basic functionality where the VS8 can make an initial call to the NSO to send the input data captured previously via the URLLC 5G network attached to this latter Network Application: the current location (longitude and latitude) and the voyage characteristics (heading and speed).

The early drop of the NSO (VS7) carries the following technical specifications:

- The NSO is a back-end REST API. Client requests deliver information using JSON via HTTPS.
- All API traffic gets encrypted with Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificates.
- For authentication, Open Authorization (OAuth) v2 is used.

3.3.1 Baseline software updates

The Navigation Speed Optimizer has not been part of any prior project, and is therefore completely developed within the VITAL-5G project.

3.4 VS8 Onboard data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II

3.4.1 Early drop features

This Network Application is a vertical-specific Network Application responsible for collecting Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) data from vessels in UC1 (i.e., location, vessel heading, and speed), and it will be made available for other VITAL-5G Network Applications and 3rd party Network Applications. This Network Application collects and processes data specific to the sensors on-boarded in the Tercofin II vessel used in UC1, while the Network Application itself is deployed in the NFV infrastructure at IMEC premises, as a part of UC1 IMEC, and it relies on the sensors deployed in the vessel at the testbed area as described in D1.1 [3].

All preliminary components are shown in Figure 25, and are available as the early drop features for this Network Application. In particular, VS8 collects, stores, and exports real-time public data coming from sensors on-boarded in the Tercofin II. These data include: speed, location, and heading, coming from the GNSS device. The Network Application receives the data over an URLLC 5G network. These data could be used by other Network Applications, possibly including 3rd party Network Applications, to collect sensor data from any other physical objects they may be deployed and interfaced with (e.g., other vessels, drones, AGV, etc.).

3.4.2 Early drop software architecture

In Figure 25, we illustrate the preliminary software architecture of VS8 Network Application, i.e., the individual software blocks such as: Public Interface, Device Specific Interface, Data Manager, and Data Storage. We describe each of these components and the technologies that are selected for their realization as follows:

- The preliminary Device Specific Interface block processes the received data coming from the Tercofin II over the 5G network, using a URLLC link. This block is realized as ZeroMQ [11] subscriber (Subscriber (VS8) in Figure 26), which is compatible with the ZeroMQ publisher running on the vessel side. The subscriber parses the data and translates it to the JSON format, which is the common standard used in the UC1 system. It further provides the Data Manager block with the JSON formatted data, which consists of speed, location, and heading, for the selected vessel in the Port of Antwerp.
- The preliminary version of the Data Manager block is in charge of storing all the received data received from the Device Specific Interface without any specific policies and/or rules to a database, and makes the selected data available to the Public Interface block. As other Network Applications might benefit from historical data for the purpose of post-processing data, or training certain ML models, in a later version of VS8 we will support managing and storing the historical data through the Data manager block.
- The preliminary Data Storage block version stores all the received data coming from the Data Manager block to a database. The database technology in the preliminary version is TinyDB [12].
- The preliminary Public Interface block makes the sensor data available in two ways through subscribing to the ZeroMQ publisher and through a REST-API where other Network Applications (i.e., VS5, VA5, VS6, and VS7) can retrieve their data, as shown in Figure 26. The data are available in different kinds of formats so that Network Applications that do not need all the data, but only need one specific type (i.e., speed, location, or heading), can easily retrieve it.

Figure 25: Preliminary software architecture of the VS8 Network Application.

In Figure 26, we present a simple overview of operations that are performed in the early version of Network Application VS8. In this way, one can clearly identify the interaction between different components such as: i) Publisher entity (grey block) on the vessel side; ii) Subscriber, Data manager, Data storage, Publisher, and REST API (green blocks) in the VS8, and iii) Subscribers (yellow block) running in other Network Applications. In particular, from the perspective of other Network Applications that are represented as Subscribers (Other Network Applications), data can be retrieved in two ways, as described above for the Public Interface block. One of them is to use the Subscriber program that listens on the topic where VS8 is publishing data, while the other one is to use REST APIs and query data anytime an update is needed.

In the case of using REST API for retrieving processed data from VS8, we provide an OpenAPI definition of this REST-based interface. In Figure 27 and Figure 28, a view on the OpenAPI calls is provided for inter-VS8 communication and external Network Applications, as well as on the VS8 OpenAPI schemas, respectively. In particular inter-VS8 calls are used internally to manage the data in the local storage (i.e., POST for creating data entries and PUT for updating them), and thus are not meant for pushing or updating data from vessel towards the VS8 Network Application. For external Network Applications we define a set of GET calls, from which full set of data (i.e., speed, location, heading) can be retrieved, or specific data that is needed, as well as the historical data that requires passing the parameter that indicates the duration (i.e., time period from which the historical data is to be retrieved, e.g., one hour).

In Figure 28 we further detail the Dataltem structure which binds all data entries (speed, coordinates, heading) together, while other schemas define format of data that can be queried separately.

Figure 26: Message sequence chart for VS8 operations.

Figure 27: OpenAPI for Public Interface of VS8.

In Figure 28 we further detail the data structure which binds all data entries (speed, coordinates, heading) together, while other schemas define format of data that can be queried separately.

Figure 28: VS8 OpenAPI Specification – Data structure.

3.4.3 IoT devices

On each vessel that is a part of UC1, a GNSS device is installed, and it generates data that consists of the latitude, longitude, speed-over-ground, course-over-ground, and heading. In particular, for VS8 the data that contains latitude, longitude, speed-over-ground, and heading, will be collected over 5G network (i.e., using 5G URLLC

slice) via subscriber running on 5G testbed. Given the operations described in Sections 3.4.1 and 3.4.2, this data is further shared with other Network Applications through VS8.

3.4.4 5G networking

In the case of VS8, it is important to ensure the 5G connectivity between the data source (vessel) and Network Applications running in the NFV infrastructure, in order to meet the requirements for low-latency and high-reliability of the network connection. This can be achieved through a URLLC slice, which will enable the required low latency and high reliability. Both latency and reliability are critical in this case, because of the sensitive data (such as speed, location, and heading, of the vessel) that needs to be consumed by other Network Applications, so that their control decisions are implemented and propagated back to vessels in a timely manner. In the future phases of testing this Network Application, URLLC slice will be created and used. However, due to the limitations in the current 5G deployment of UC1, in this initial phase of VS8 implementation and testing, an EMBB slice will be defined with a sufficient bandwidth.

3.4.5 Software licenses and link to repositories

The preliminary version of VS8 will be available as a Docker image on the Docker Hub repository available on the following link: <https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/ninask92/vital-5g/>. The access to Docker image (push and pull access) will be granted to collaborators by adding them to the repository.

3.4.6 Baseline software updates

This software module is a newly developed Network Application for the purpose of interfacing with and collected data from the Tercofin II vessel. Its design and development (including interfaces with the other Network Applications) are defined and executed within the confines of the VITAL-5G project.

4 Conclusions

The main conclusion of this document is that the project has successfully delivered the early drop version of the VITAL-5G Platform, covering most of the catalogue management services and initial support for service lifecycle management capabilities, and early drop of four different Network Applications mainly covering the field sensor data ingestion capabilities, and initial demonstration of a Network Application providing optimization capabilities.

The main objective of this document is to describe the software components, features and delivery mechanisms of the different components of the VITAL-5G platform and the VITAL-5G Network Applications in the early drop version. In Section 2, a comprehensive description of the five different modules is given including also their functionalities. We described how we can enable the seamless support of onboarding and managing of Network Application packages, Vertical Service and Experiment Blueprints (together with their associated descriptors) with the overall aim to show how the Network Application concept can accommodate the overall service design phase. Moreover, initial Vertical Service and Experiment Lifecycle management is also supported in order to provide proof of the validity of the overall approach.

In Section 3 we describe the early versions of four different Network Applications covering vertical-specific and vertical-agnostic functionalities, as well as functional logic from the three different use cases of the project. More specifically, the VA1 *“Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation”* that is responsible for the data ingestion and two-way communication with on-site equipment, decision support using rules and inference, monitoring and field assistance. VA2 *“Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & automation”* that supports data ingestion, fusion and post-processing functionalities from distributed data sources. VS7 *“Navigation Speed Optimizer”* that is retrieving in real-time all the data needed to calculate the optimal navigation speed for a vessel. VS8 *“On board data collection & interfacing for vessel Tercofin II”* that is collecting GNSS data from vessels in UC1 (i.e., location, vessel heading, and speed).

The VITAL-5G Platform components have been successfully deployed in the testbed development environment, while the Network Applications have been deployed in the different testbeds. This allowed Network Application developers to start using and getting familiar with the functionalities and interfaces of the platform for catalogue management and initial service lifecycle management capabilities.

The next drop of the VITAL-5G platform and Network Applications will shift the focus to support monitoring, reporting and automated analytics capabilities, and the introduction of AI/ML tools in the Network Applications and in the service and experiment lifecycle management procedures.

5 References

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